

Presentation

These articles were originally published in the *Pedagogy Series*, housed on the ISA's *Social Justice and Democratization Space* in January 2021. We are republishing it in order to standardize all the articles in the *Sociological Teaching* journal.

Dear colleagues,

Welcome to the first issue of the ISA's new *Pedagogy Series*, a triannual publication facilitating transnational exchange of research and reflections on sociology teaching and pedagogy in sociology. This publication is a collaboration between the ISA's *Social Justice and Democratization Space* – a dynamic portal for a global community of sociologists – and the ISA's new thematic group, *Sociological Teaching*. *Sociological Teaching* brings together international sociologists who have a research interest in the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning, specialize in teaching sociology, and incorporate sociological insights into their teaching practices.

This first issue features scholars' analyses of and reflections upon the transition to teaching sociology remotely due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Contributions in this January issue come from sociologists working in South Africa, Brazil, and Germany. The five articles shine a light on numerous facets of this challenging time, including the digital divides constraining and enabling student learning opportunities, sociology pedagogies suitable to the remote context, and the gendered nature of COVID-19 labour.

The first two papers, written by Andrea Breitenbach and Sultan Khan respectively, grapple with layered digital divides shaping access to remote education in diverse national contexts. Breitenbach considers how students' remote education is influenced not only by digital access, but by digital acceptance and competency informed by socio-demographic factors. Drawing upon survey data from Germany

and the United States, Breitenbach demonstrates how certain groups of students struggle more with the switch to digital teaching than others. Khan situates the digital divide within national context to consider how this divide structures access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) at the institutional level within post-liberation South Africa. Khan presents a case study of the University of Kwazulu-Natal and its COVID-19 response, with reference to deepening ICT inequities between historically advantaged white universities and disadvantaged Black universities in the nation, informed by legacies of colonialism and Apartheid.

Written by João Marcelo E. Maia and Isabel Steinhardt respectively, the third and fourth papers focus on the pedagogical implication of remote teaching for sociology educators. Reflecting on persistent inequities in Brazil's higher education system, Maia uses the unexpected experience of emergency online teaching as a reflexive opportunity to build on Halasz and Kaufman's (2008) call for educators to approach sociology *as* pedagogy. In Germany, Steinhardt details the challenges students face in digital education and how she addressed some of these challenges through course design, centering collaborative autoethnography as a process for creating a digital community of learning.

The final article is a critical piece contributed by Mariam Seedat-Khan and Aradhana Ramnund-Mansingh. The authors unpack the implications of gendered shifts in teaching labour for women faculty in South Africa due to COVID-19. They systematically document considerations for promoting gender equity in academia in a time when gender inequities appear to be deepening.

Thank you very much for your readership and support for this new ISA publication.

From the Editors